

FT-008

Enhanced Photocurrent Response of ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe Quantum Dot-Sensitized Heterostructure Under Simulated Solar Light

Mesut ERYİĞİT^{1*} ^{1*} *Balıkesir University Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science and Art, 10145, Balıkesir, Türkiye*² *Gebze Technical University, Faculty of Science, Department of Chemistry, Kocaeli, Türkiye*

*mesut.eryigit@balikesir.edu.tr, demiru@gtu.edu.tr

*Corresponding Author

Abstract— Efficient solar energy conversion is crucial for sustainable energy technologies, and the development of quantum dot-sensitized heterostructured photoanodes with high photocurrent response has attracted considerable attention. In this study, an ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ nanocomposite photoanode was synthesized via an electrochemical method, while PbS and CdSe quantum dots (QDs) were deposited using the successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) technique. The electrochemical approach was selected because it enables rapid, controllable, and direct film formation on conductive substrates. Initially, a Zn(OH)₂/ERGO structure was formed on FTO, followed by the deposition of a Zn(OH)₂/ERGO@TiO(OH)₂ precursor in a Ti-containing electrolyte. Subsequent annealing at 500 °C for 2 h transformed the hydroxide phases into oxide phases, yielding the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ photoanode. PbS and CdSe QDs were then sequentially deposited through 15 and 3 SILAR cycles, respectively. Photoelectrochemical measurements under simulated solar illumination demonstrated that the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe photoanode achieved a photocurrent density of 15.21 mA cm⁻², significantly higher than those of the control electrodes. The enhanced performance was attributed to the synergistic effect of the heterostructure and dual-QD sensitization, which improved light harvesting and promoted efficient separation of photogenerated electron–hole pairs. Structural, morphological, optical, and electrochemical properties of the synthesized nanocomposites were investigated using XRD, XPS, EDS, FESEM, UV–Vis spectroscopy, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

Keywords: Electrochemical Synthesis; ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂; Heterostructure; Photocurrent; Quantum Dot Sensitization; SILAR.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing global energy demand and environmental concerns associated with the extensive use of fossil fuels have accelerated the search for sustainable and renewable energy sources. Among the available alternatives, solar energy is considered one of the most promising resources due to its abundance, cleanliness, and long-term availability. Efficient conversion of solar energy into usable forms has therefore become a major research focus in the fields of materials science, nanotechnology, and photoelectrochemistry [1].

Photoelectrochemical (PEC) systems have attracted considerable attention for solar energy conversion because they can directly convert solar energy into electrical or chemical energy through light-induced charge generation and transfer processes [2]. The performance of PEC devices is strongly influenced by

the structural, optical, and electronic properties of the photoanode materials [3]. Among various semiconductor materials, zinc oxide (ZnO) and titanium dioxide (TiO₂) are widely employed owing to their low cost, chemical stability, environmental compatibility, and suitable electronic structures. However, their relatively wide band gaps limit visible-light absorption, while rapid electron–hole recombination reduces overall photoelectrochemical efficiency [4,5].

To overcome these limitations, graphene-based materials have been extensively incorporated into semiconductor systems [6]. Electrochemically reduced graphene oxide (ERGO) possesses excellent electrical conductivity, high electron mobility, and a large specific surface area, making it an attractive component for photoelectrochemical applications [7]. The incorporation of ERGO into metal oxide structures can facilitate charge transport, suppress charge recombination, and improve the collection efficiency of photogenerated electrons [8].

Quantum dots (QDs) have emerged as highly efficient sensitizers due to their size-dependent optical properties, tunable band gaps, broad absorption range, and high extinction coefficients [9]. Compared with conventional molecular dyes, QDs exhibit superior photostability and enhanced light-harvesting capability [10]. In particular, lead sulfide (PbS) quantum dots possess strong absorption in the visible and near-infrared regions, whereas cadmium selenide (CdSe) quantum dots exhibit favorable optical properties and suitable band alignment with semiconductor photoanodes [11,12]. The combination of different quantum dots in a multilayer sensitization strategy can further improve light absorption and promote efficient charge separation through cascade electron-transfer pathways [13].

Although numerous studies have investigated ZnO-, TiO₂-, graphene-, and quantum dot-based photoelectrode, studies focusing on electrochemically synthesized ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructures sensitized with dual PbS/CdSe quantum dots remain limited. Therefore, the development of such heterostructures is of significant interest for improving photoelectrochemical performance and solar energy utilization [14,15].

In this study, an ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructure photoanode was fabricated through a two-step electrochemical deposition process followed by thermal annealing. Initially, a Zn(OH)₂/ERGO structure was electrodeposited onto an FTO substrate from an aqueous electrolyte containing Zn²⁺ ions and graphene oxide (GO). Subsequently, a Zn(OH)₂/ERGO@TiO(OH)₂ precursor was formed by electrodeposition in a Ti-containing electrolyte. The obtained precursor was annealed at 500 °C for 2 h to convert the hydroxide phases into oxide phases, resulting in the formation of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ photoanode. To enhance visible-light harvesting, PbS and CdSe quantum dots were sequentially deposited onto the photoanode surface through 15 and 3 successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) cycles, respectively. The structural, morphological, optical, and electrochemical properties of the synthesized nanocomposites were investigated using X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), ultraviolet–visible (UV–Vis) spectroscopy, and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Furthermore, the photoelectrochemical performance of the fabricated photoanodes was evaluated under simulated solar illumination, and the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe heterostructure exhibited a maximum photocurrent density of 15.21 mA cm⁻².

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) coated glass substrates ($10\text{--}12 \Omega \text{ sq}^{-1}$) were used as conductive substrates for photoanode fabrication. Graphene oxide (GO), zinc acetate dihydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), titanium precursor, lead acetate trihydrate ($\text{Pb}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$), cadmium acetate dihydrate ($\text{Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium sulfide (Na_2S), selenium dioxide (SeO_2), sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4), and sodium sulfite (Na_2SO_3) were used as received without further purification. Deionized water was employed for the preparation of all aqueous solutions. All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade and purchased from commercial suppliers.

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. Synthesis of ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ Photoanode

The ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ photoanode was synthesized through a two-step electrochemical deposition process using an FTO-coated glass substrate as the working electrode. In the first step, Zn^{2+} ions and graphene oxide (GO) were co-deposited onto the FTO substrate from an aqueous electrolyte under an applied potential of -1.1 V for 30 min, resulting in the formation of a $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2/\text{ERGO}$ structure. Subsequently, the obtained electrode was immersed in a Ti-containing electrolyte and electrodeposited at -1.4 V for 15 min to form a $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2/\text{ERGO}@ \text{TiO}(\text{OH})_2$ precursor. The precursor electrode was then annealed at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h in air to convert the hydroxide phases into oxide phases, yielding the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructure photoanode.

2.2.2. Deposition of PbS and CdSe Quantum Dots by SILAR

PbS and CdSe quantum dots were sequentially deposited onto the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ photoanode using the successive ionic layer adsorption and reaction (SILAR) technique. For PbS deposition, the photoanode was alternately immersed in $0.05 \text{ M Pb}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and $0.1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{S}$ solutions for 20 s each, followed by rinsing with deionized water. This procedure was repeated for 15 SILAR cycles to obtain the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS photoanode.

Subsequently, CdSe quantum dots were deposited onto the PbS-modified photoanode. The electrode was alternately immersed in $0.1 \text{ M Cd}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ and Se^{2-} precursor solutions prepared from 0.05 M SeO_2 and 1 M NaBH_4 for 20 s each. After each immersion step, the electrode was rinsed with deionized water to remove loosely attached species. The deposition procedure was repeated for 3 SILAR cycles, resulting in the formation of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode. The synthesis route of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode is schematically illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the electrochemical synthesis of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructure and subsequent PbS/CdSe quantum dot sensitization via the SILAR method.

2.2.3. Characterization and Photoelectrochemical Measurements

The crystal structure and phase composition of the synthesized photoanodes were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Surface chemical states were analyzed using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), while morphological characteristics were examined by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Optical properties were evaluated using UV–Vis absorption spectroscopy. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed to investigate charge-transfer characteristics.

Photoelectrochemical measurements were conducted in a conventional three-electrode system using the synthesized photoanodes as the working electrode, Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode, and Pt wire as the counter electrode. Simulated solar illumination (AM 1.5G) was employed as the light source. The photocurrent responses and current–voltage (*I*–*V*) characteristics of the photoanodes were recorded to evaluate their photoelectrochemical performance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows the XRD patterns of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ and ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe photoanodes prepared on FTO substrates. The diffraction peaks observed at 25.3°, 37.8°, 48.0°, 53.9°, 55.1°, and 62.7° correspond to the (101), (004), (200), (105), (211), and (204) crystal planes of anatase TiO₂, respectively. In addition, the characteristic diffraction peaks of hexagonal wurtzite ZnO are clearly visible, indicating that the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructure remained stable after PbS/CdSe sensitization. Furthermore, diffraction peaks located at 25.4°, 49.7°, 60.1°, 67.1°, and 76.8° were assigned to hexagonal CdSe, while peaks at 25.4° and 47.2° were attributed to orthorhombic PbS quantum dots. The overlap of several PbS and CdSe diffraction peaks is associated with their similar crystallographic positions. The absence of the characteristic ERGO peak near 25° may be attributed to peak overlap with the intense diffraction peaks of TiO₂ and ZnO. These results confirm the successful deposition of PbS/CdSe quantum dots onto the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ surface through the SILAR process. The average crystallite size of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe photoanode was calculated using the Debye–Scherrer equation and was found to be approximately 30.8 nm.

Figure. 2. Comparison of XRD diffraction peaks for ZnO and ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-Pbs/CdSe photoanodes.

The chemical composition and electronic structure of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-Pbs/CdSe nanocomposites were investigated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and the results are presented in Figure 3. As shown in the survey spectrum (Figure 3a), all detected peaks can be assigned to C, O, Ti, Zn, Pb, Cd, Se, and S elements, confirming the successful formation of the composite structure. The high-resolution Cd 3d spectrum (Figure 3b) exhibits two characteristic peaks at 404.7 and 411.5 eV, corresponding to Cd 3d_{5/2} and Cd 3d_{3/2}, respectively, indicating the presence of Cd²⁺ ions in CdSe. In addition, the peak located at 55.1 eV is attributed to Se 3d. As shown in Figure 3c, the peaks observed at 139.0 and 143.8 eV correspond to Pb 4f_{7/2} and Pb 4f_{5/2}, respectively, confirming the presence of Pb²⁺ ions in PbS. Furthermore, the Se 3d peak at 55.1 eV and the S 2p peak at 161.5 eV (Figure 3d–e) verify the existence of Se²⁻ and S²⁻ species in the deposited quantum dots. The obtained binding energies are in good agreement with the reported literature values, confirming the successful deposition of PbS/CdSe quantum dots onto the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ surface via the SILAR method.

Figure 3. XPS spectra of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode: (a) survey spectrum; (b) Cd 3d; (c) Pb 4f; (d) Se 3d; (e) S 2p.

The surface morphology and elemental composition of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode were investigated by FESEM and EDS analyses, as shown in Figure 4. The FESEM images (Figure 4a–b) reveal a porous and highly roughened surface composed of densely packed nanostructures, providing a large active surface area for quantum dot loading and photoelectrochemical reactions. In addition, the uniform distribution of nanosized particles on the electrode surface indicates the successful deposition of PbS and CdSe quantum dots. The EDS spectrum (Figure 4c) confirms the presence of Zn, Ti, O, Pb, Cd, Se, and S elements, which is consistent with the XRD and XPS results. These findings demonstrate the successful formation of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe heterostructure and suggest that the porous morphology is favorable for enhanced light harvesting and charge-transfer processes.

Figure 4. FESEM images of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode recorded at different magnifications: (a) 1,000× and (b) 10,000×. (c) EDS spectrum confirming the presence of Zn, Ti, O, Pb, Cd, Se, and S elements in the synthesized heterostructure.

The optical and photoelectrochemical properties of the synthesized photoanodes were investigated using UV-Vis spectroscopy, Tauc analysis, EIS, and photocurrent measurements, as shown in Figure 5. The UV-Vis spectra (Figure 5a) reveal that PbS/CdSe sensitization significantly enhanced light absorption in the visible region compared to the bare ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ photoanode. The Tauc plot (Figure 5b) indicates an optical band gap of approximately 2.2 eV for the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode, confirming the extension of light harvesting toward the visible region. Furthermore, the Nyquist plots obtained from EIS measurements (Figure 5c) show that the sensitized photoanode exhibits a much smaller semicircle diameter, indicating lower charge-transfer resistance and more efficient electron transport. Consistent with these findings, photocurrent measurements under chopped simulated solar illumination (Figure 5d) demonstrate a remarkable enhancement in photocurrent density, reaching approximately 15.21 mA cm⁻² for the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂-PbS/CdSe photoanode. The improved performance is attributed to the synergistic effect of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructure and dual PbS/CdSe quantum dot sensitization, which promotes light harvesting, charge separation, and electron-transfer efficiency.

Figure 5. (a) UV–Vis absorption spectra of ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ and ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe photoanodes, (b) Tauc plot used for the determination of the optical band gap of ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe, (c) Nyquist plots obtained from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), and (d) transient photocurrent responses of the synthesized photoanodes under simulated solar illumination.

4. CONCLUSION

In summary, an ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe heterostructure photoanode was successfully fabricated through electrochemical deposition followed by SILAR-assisted quantum dot sensitization. XRD, XPS, FESEM, and EDS analyses confirmed the successful formation of the heterostructure and the deposition of PbS/CdSe quantum dots. UV–Vis results demonstrated enhanced visible-light absorption, while EIS measurements revealed reduced charge-transfer resistance after sensitization. The ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂–PbS/CdSe photoanode exhibited a significantly improved photocurrent density of 15.21 mA cm⁻² under simulated solar illumination, owing to the synergistic effects of the ERGO/ZnO@TiO₂ heterostructure and dual quantum dot sensitization. Furthermore, the electrochemical synthesis route provided a simple, controllable, and environmentally friendly approach for the simultaneous reduction of graphene oxide and formation of metal oxide nanostructures without the use of toxic reducing agents. These findings suggest that the proposed heterostructure is a promising candidate for photoelectrochemical energy conversion applications. Moreover, owing to its enhanced light-harvesting capability, efficient charge separation, and large active surface area, the synthesized heterostructure may also find potential applications in photocatalytic hydrogen production, environmental remediation, photoelectrochemical sensing, and self-powered optoelectronic devices.

Acknowledge

The authors gratefully acknowledge Gebze Technical University for providing the research facilities and laboratory infrastructure used in this study. This work was financially supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK) through the BİDEB 2218 – National Postdoctoral Research Fellowship Program under Project No. 118C585.

This study was presented as an oral presentation at the 9th International Conference on Physical Chemistry and Functional Materials (PCFM 2026), held on May 8–9, 2026.

Author Contributions (Compulsory)

Mesut Eryiğit conducted this study as part of his TÜBİTAK BİDEB 2218 – National Postdoctoral Research Fellowship Program, conceived and designed the research, performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and prepared the original draft of the manuscript. Ümit Demir supervised the postdoctoral research, contributed to data interpretation, and critically reviewed and revised the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest (Compulsory)

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Review and Approval (Compulsory)

No ethical approval is required.

References

- [1] S. Monika, et al., TiO₂/CdS/CdSe quantum dots co-sensitized solar cell with the staggered-gap (type-II) heterojunctions for the enhanced photovoltaic performance. *Ceramics International*, 2023, 49(6): 8820–8826. DOI: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2022.11.034.
- [2] R. A. Pawar, et al., Nanocrystalline TiO₂ sensitized with CdS quantum dots for photoelectrochemical study. *Applied Physics A*, 2023, 129: 559. DOI: 10.1007/s00339-023-06833-5.
- [3] A. S. Rasal, et al., Stability of quantum dot-sensitized solar cells: A review and prospects. *Nano Energy*, 2022, 94: 106854. DOI: 10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.106854.
- [4] E. P. Gür, et al., High-performance PbS/CdS quantum dot co-sensitized hierarchical ZnO nanowall photoanodes decorated on electrochemically reduced graphene. *Electrochimica Acta*, 2023, 438: 141584. DOI: 10.1016/j.electacta.2022.141584.
- [5] E. Temur, et al., Electrochemical fabrication and reductive doping of electrochemically reduced graphene oxide decorated with TiO₂ electrode with highly enhanced photoresponse under visible light. *Applied Surface Science*, 2022, 581: 152150. DOI: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2021.152150.
- [6] K. Wang, et al., Stability of photoelectrochemical cells based on colloidal quantum dots. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 2025, 54: 3513–3534. DOI: 10.1039/D4CS00587B.
- [7] G. Shilpa, et al., Recent advances in the development of high efficiency quantum dot sensitized solar cells (QDSSCs): A review. *Materials Science for Energy Technologies*, 2023, 6: 533–546. DOI: 10.1016/j.mset.2023.05.001.
- [8] A. S. Najm, et al., Recent progress in performance improvement strategies for quantum dot sensitization methods: Challenges, achievements, and future prospects. *APL Materials*, 2023, 11(9): 090601. DOI: 10.1063/5.0166032.
- [9] Z. Zhang, et al., Improving the efficiency of quantum dot-sensitized solar cells by increasing the QD loading amount. *Chemical Science*, 2024, 15(15): 5482–5495. DOI: 10.1039/D3SC06911G.

- [10] M. Eryiğit, et al., Efficient CdS quantum dot sensitized solar cells based on electrochemically reduced graphene oxide (ERGO)/ZnO nanowall photoanodes and MoS₂, WS₂, CuS cascaded counter electrodes. *Solar Energy*, 2022, 234: 348–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.solener.2022.01.030.
- [11] P. Mazierski, et al., Ti/TiO₂ nanotubes sensitized PbS quantum dots as photoelectrodes applied for decomposition of anticancer drugs under simulated solar energy. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2022, 421: 126751. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.126751.
- [12] E. Akyürek, et al., Efficient photoelectrochemical H₂ generation via electrochemically modified TiO₂/electrochemically reduced graphene oxide photoelectrode with Ti³⁺ defects and Mg(OH)₂ nanoplates. *Materials Research Bulletin*, 2024, 180: 113014. DOI: 10.1016/j.materresbull.2024.113014.
- [13] J. Zhang, et al., Colloidal quantum dots: Synthesis, composition, structure, and emerging optoelectronic applications. *Laser & Photonics Reviews*, 2023, 17(3): 2200551. DOI: 10.1002/lpor.202200551.
- [14] H. Lu, et al., One-step electrodeposition of ZnO/graphene composites with enhanced capability for photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes. *Frontiers in Chemistry*, 2022, 10: 1061129. DOI: 10.3389/fchem.2022.1061129.
- [15] L. Yu, et al., CdS/CdSe/PbS quantum dots sensitized TiO₂ eggshell hollow microspheres photoanode to boost photocurrent and power conversion efficiency of QDSSC. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 2024, 452: 115607. DOI: 10.1016/j.jphotochem.2024.115607.